

RESPONSE PAPER

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FIRST NAME: EMMANUEL

PROGRAM CODE: DDIA

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE PERIOD SIX

1. What are the elements to look out for in considering if research is pure?
 - The methodology is consistent with the research question
 - The literature review is in sync with the research implication
 - “When it addresses a conceptual problem that does not have any direct practical consequences, when it only improves the understanding of a community of researchers.”¹**
 - When it addresses a conceptual problem, that does have practical consequences
2. Apply What are the two parts of a structure to consider when considering practical and conceptual research problems?
 - “A situation or condition and undesirable costs or consequences caused by that condition.”²**
 - The situation and consequence are a particular kind of ignorance
 - Practical and conceptual problems are most common in the professional world.

¹ Kate, L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertation*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

² Ibid.

- Undesirable costs and consequences caused by that condition
 - Practical problems are most common in the professional world; conceptual problems are most common in academics.
3. Which of the following best describes a research assumption when conducting research?
- Research is an assumption to consider when conducting a scientific study
 - Research assumptions are a combination of the research question, objective, and methodology
 - Research assumptions are those elements in a scientific study that are supported by the methodology
 - “Research assumptions are ideas you believe to be true but do not have evidence to support.”³**
4. Which of the following best describes the rationale for a research design?
- The justification for selecting the research setting provides the history, background, and issues germane to the problem.
 - The process of all data collection methods, tools, instruments, and procedures, including how, when, where, and by whom data were collected.
 - “The approach and the research methodology with a rationale for their suitability regarding addressing the research questions and citing appropriate methodological literature.”⁴**
 - The justification for all methods and tools used to analyze data (manual and/or computational).
5. Which of the following is not a necessary requirement in mentioning the source of information when writing an academic paper?
- It is not fair to take someone’s work and not give them credit
 - “It increases someone’s academic grading.”⁵**
 - It is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences
 - Plagiarism is wrong and unethical

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* Fourth Edition (California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 80.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma., *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*,. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34

6. To make WHO information products accessible by all users of English, it does not encourage the use of the following except?
- The use of both British and your Native language spelling
 - “The use of a mix of British and North American spelling.”**⁶
 - The use of British spelling only for ease of communication
 - The use of a mix of British, American, and your native spelling
7. In the WHO rule of style, the bibliography is given at the end of one of the following.
- At the end of a publication after the index
 - At the end of a publication after the appendix
 - “At the end of a publication, before the index.”**⁷
 - At the end of a publication, after the index, and before the appendix
8. The dissertation concept paper, sometimes referred to as a pre-prospectus paper, consists of the following elements.
- Is a research proposal that describes the research methodology and its research variables that will be used for the study proposal that discusses the research outcome and its implication
 - Is a research process that describes gap in the literature and proposes how the void will be filled
 - “Is a research proposal that describes what might be studied in the proposed dissertation, why it needs to be studied, and how it might be studied.”**⁸
 - Is a research proposal that describes data analysis processes and a proposal of how it will be used to advance knowledge
9. According to EU legislation, which of the following is the preferred and appropriate gender-neutral language to use?

⁶ WHO, *WHO Style Guide.*, Second Edition (WHO, 2013), 13.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 43.

⁸ James, P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research.* Second Edition (Florida: Florida State University 2017), 9.

- The use of nouns such as ‘chairman’ or ‘chairwoman’ appear to assume that persons of both gender habitually perform a particular role
- “Gender-neutral noun forms (chair, spokesperson, etc.) are preferred.”⁹**
- If the text clearly refers to a specific individual on a particular occasion, and you know the gender of the person concerned, use a gender-specific pronoun
- Use words such as ‘man-made’ or ‘woman-made’ that refer to people of all genders.

10. In the European Union, the “geographical terms” refers to the following

- The European Union is referred to systematically as ‘the Union’ of all communities in Europe in accordance with Lisbon Treaties and legislations.
- “The European Union comprises the combined territories of its Members States.”¹⁰**
- The European Union comprises all Member states operating a single market, including the U.K., France, and Germany.
- The European Union also Comprises other regional bodies such as the AU and Arab League

⁹ European Union, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* Eight Edition (European, 2021), 73.

¹⁰ Ibid.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth. California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

European Union. *English Style Guide A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eight Edition, 2021.

Sampson, P. James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Florida: Florida State University, 2017

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students*. Ninth Edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. Second Edition. WHO, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.